

Electrospray Differential Mobility Analysis (ES-DMA)

**Deliverable 3.3, SOPs for all Physicochemical Methods,
Annex I, page 105.**

SOP for ES-DMA

This instruction describes the standard operation procedure for particle size characterization of anionic colloidal silica in the 2-64 nm size range, using electrospray differential mobility analysis (ES-DMA).

IMPORTANT: Cat-ionic particles may block the capillary of the electrospray and should therefore never be analyzed by ES-DMA.

Method

The following settings and conditions are used:

Carrier solution	20 mM ammonium acetate with pH 8
Carrier flow	12 µl/min
Electrospray voltage	approx. 1.7 kV / 400 nA, adjusted until a stable electrospray is acquired
Electrospray air flow	1,500 l/min
Electrospray CO2 flow	0,100 l/min
DMA Sheet flow	15 l/min
DMA Sweep time	30 s

Start of the computer

Start the computer and log in.

Start the software "MacroIMS-5" using the desktop icon.

Click "Login"

Under "Select Project", select <New project> and name it by your signature and the date.

If the dialog box "Sampler 1: The rack detected on the hardware differs from the one specified in the method" is open, click "OK".

Three new windows should now be opened:

Instrument 1 – Method Noname

Instrument 1 – Sequence Noname

Instrument 1 – Data Acquisition

Open Explorer, copy the five files in the folder C:\TSI\MacroIMS-5\Standard methods and paste them in the folder with the same name as your new project.

From the window "Instrument 1 – Method Noname", choose "File – Open Method" and select the method "NDMA4 2to64nm 30s LC12 RT15 IDLE+CO2.MET". The instrument will now adjust pump flow rates for the analysis.

From the window "Instrument 1 – Sequence Noname", select "File – New" and create a new sequence file.

Start of the instrument

Open the CO₂ valve (A) on the wall.

Turn the reduction valve (B) to a pressure of 0,5 bars.

Open the valve (C) completely (1-2 turns).

Adjust the CO₂ flow to 0.100 ± 0.005 l/min using the reduction valve (B).

Adjust the flow of compressed air to 1.500 ± 0.010 l/min using the control knob (D).

Ensure that the electrospray is forming a stable Taylor-cone at a voltage of 1.7 kV / 400 nA. If not, adjust the voltage until the electrospray is stable.

Sample preparation

Rinse a 1 ml vial with 20 mmol/l ammonium acetate buffer

Add an appropriate volume of sample, and dilute with 20 mmol/l ammonium acetate to a volume of 0,5-1 ml. For the appropriate sample volume, use the following recommendations:

For particles <15 nm: dilute to maximum 50 ppm

For particles 15-30 nm: dilute to maximum 100 ppm

For particles 30-50 nm: dilute to maximum 200 ppm

For particles >50 nm: dilute to maximum 500 ppm

(e.g., 0,5 μ l of 40% colloidal silica diluted to 0,5 ml will result in a concentration of 400 ppm)

Higher concentrations than 500 ppm can result in blockage of the electrospray capillary.